

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-*S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides

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Abstract : A new series 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-*S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides have been synthesized by the interaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets and phenyl isocyanodichloride. The newly synthesized compounds have been characterised by analytical and IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies. These newly synthesized thiolactosides are also tested for antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Keywords : Lactosyl isodithiobiurets, phenyl isocyanodichloride, lactosyl thiadiazines.

Introduction

Today heterocycles are known to have wide variety of biological functions. Sulphur containing glycolipids¹, derivatives of imidazole², thiadiazines³⁻⁵, triazines⁶ have pharmaceutical importance. Some reports showing general routes for preparation of 1,3,5-thiadiazines are found. Such *N* and *S* lactosylated derivatives exhibit a wide range of medicinal activities, such as antiviral, antidiabetic, analgesic, antitumor and some other activities⁷. The chemistry of organo-sulphur systems^{8,9} prompted us to extend our work into a series of lactosyl-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides. The preparation of this heterocyclic ring is mostly achieved by heterocyclisation of lactosyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets¹⁰. We report here in the simple method for the synthesis of 1,3,5-thiadiazine by the interaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets and phenyl isocyanodichloride. The required *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets have been obtained by the interaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1-arylthiocarbamides and arylthiocarbamides.

Results and discussion

Several 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-*S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (**5a-g**) have been prepared by the reaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3a-g**)

and phenyl isocyanodichloride (**4**) in CHCl₃ medium, evolution of HCl was noticed. After condensation the solvent was distilled off and the resulting syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid. The products were purified by ethanol-water.

The structure of the products were confirmed by spectral analysis (IR¹¹, NMR¹² and Mass¹³). The specific rotation of the products were also recorded¹⁴. All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Experimental

All the melting points recorded are found uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI FTIR spectrometer. ¹H NMR was obtained on Bruker DRX-300 NMR spectrometer. Samples were prepared in CDCl₃ with TMS as an internal reference. The mass spectra were obtained on Thermo Fennigan LCQ Advantage max ion trap mass spectrometer. Optical rotations [α]_D³¹ were measured on the Equip-Tronics EQ-800 Digital Polarimeter at 31 °C in CHCl₃.

General procedure :

*Preparation of 1-arylthiocarbamides*¹⁵ :

The required 1-arylthiocarbamides were prepared by already known method i.e. by interaction of appropriate aryl amine hydrochloride and ammonium thiocyanate.

where, Bz = COC_6H_5 ; R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Scheme 2

Preparation of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1-phenylisothiocarbamide¹⁶ (1a) (Scheme 1) :

Isopropanolic (40 ml) suspension of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl bromide (0.005 M, 5.66 g) and phenyl thiocarbamide (0.005 M, 0.76 g) was heated on water bath at about 70 °C until the suspension gets cleared. The clear solution was kept at room temperature for 20 h.

The aqueous solution when basified with aqueous

ammonia a sticky mass was separated out which was not solidified on standing for several hours. This sticky mass was failed to afford solid when triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C). The sticky mass was purified by ethanol-water and the solid mass was obtained, (1a) (4.1 g, 69.49%), m.p. 94 °C.

Synthesis of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret¹⁷ (3a) (Scheme 1) :

A mixture of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1-

phenylisothiocarbamide (**1a**) (0.0025 M, 3.01 g) and phenyl isothiocyanate (**2**) (0.0025 M, 0.33 g) in dry benzene was refluxed for 9 h. The benzene was distilled off. The sticky mass obtained was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) furnishing a crystalline solid (**3a**) (3 g). It was purified with ethanol-water (2.7 g, 87.53%), m.p. 145–147 °C.

Preparation of phenyl isocyanodichloride¹⁸ (4) :

The phenyl isocyanodichloride was prepared by the interaction of phenyl isothiocyanate and excess of chlorine. Details of a typical experiment are as follows :

Through a chloroform solution of phenyl isothiocyanate (7 ml in 15 ml chloroform) chlorine (generated from 10 g KMnO_4) and 70 ml conc. HCl was passed maintaining the temperature below 10 °C. After complete addition of chlorine, the yellow reaction mixture was diluted with (40 ml) dry petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and filtered to remove suspended impurities. The solvent was then removed by distillation under vacuum. The whole process was repeated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and finally the petroleum ether distilled off and phenyl isocyanodichloride in the form of pale yellow oil was collected (Found : N, 7.95, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NCl}_2$ required : N, 8.04%).

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-S-hepta-O-benzoyl-lactosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (5a) (Scheme 2) :

Condensation of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (**3a**) (0.002 M, 2.67 g) with phenyl isocyanodichloride (**4**) (0.002 M, 0.35 g) in chloroform (40 ml) was carried out for 3 h. The evolution of

hydrogen chloride was noticed, afterwards the excess of chloroform was distilled off and resultant viscous residue triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C, 60 ml) to afford a pale yellow solid (**5a**). It was purified with ethanol-water (2.2 g, 79%), m.p. 159 °C.

On extending the reaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets with phenyl isocyanodichloride several 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-*S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides have been isolated (**5b-g**) (Table 1).

Spectral data :

(**3a**) : m.p. 159 °C; yield 79%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 113^\circ$ (*c*, 0.156 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : ν 3453 (N-H), 3067.5 (Ar-H stretching), 2970 (ali. C-H), 1729.1 (C=O), 1541.7 (C=N), 1270.4 (C-O), 708 (C-S), 1026, 858 cm^{-1} (characteristic of lactose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : 8.09–7.16 (50H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ protons), 4.95–3.71 (12H, m, lactosyl protons), 5.78–5.69 (2H, s, anomeric lactosyl protons); MS (*m/z*) : 1476.5 (M^+), 1477.5 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 1440 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{HCl}$), 1053 (HBL⁺), 948 (HBL⁺ - COC_6H_5), 932 (HBL⁺ - COOC_6H_5), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺ - $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$), 335 (TBG - $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$) (Found : C, 66.43; H, 4.18; N, 3.02; S, 4.13. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{82}\text{H}_{64}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$: C, 66.64; H, 4.33; N, 3.7; S, 4.33%).

(**3b**) : m.p. 129–130 °C; yield 72%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 86^\circ$ (*c*, 0.156 in CHCl_3) (Found : C, 65.04; H, 4.08; N, 3.21; S, 4.15. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{82}\text{H}_{63}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl} \cdot \text{HCl}$: C, 65.12; H, 4.16; N, 3.70; S, 4.23%).

(**3c**) : m.p. 134–136 °C; yield 79%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 118^\circ$ (*c*, 0.156 in CHCl_3) (Found : C, 65.08; H, 4.13; N, 3.56; S,

Table 1. 3-Aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-*S*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (**5a-g**) (Scheme 2)

Reactants : (I) *S*-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl-lactosyl-1-aryl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3a-g**) (0.002 M), (II) phenyl isocyanodichloride (**4**) (0.002 M in 15 ml CHCl_3)

Product	Melting point (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Requires)		$[\alpha]_D^{28}$ (<i>c</i> , 0.156, CHCl_3)
			N	S	
3a	159	79	3.02 (3.7)	4.13 (4.33)	+113°
3b	129–130	72	3.21 (3.70)	4.15 (4.23)	+95°
3c	134–136	79	3.56 (3.70)	4.18 (4.23)	+130°
3d	146–148	71	3.43 (3.70)	4.12 (4.23)	+105°
3e	114–116	68	3.22 (3.75)	4.03 (4.29)	+118°
3f	106–108	74	3.12 (3.75)	4.18 (4.29)	+98°
3g	138	78	3.22 (3.75)	4.03 (4.29)	+110°

Satisfactory C and H analysis were found in all cases.

4.18. Calcd. for $C_{82}H_{63}O_{17}N_4S_2Cl.HCl$: C, 65.12; H, 4.16; N, 3.70; S, 4.23%.

(3d): m.p. 146–148 °C; yield 71%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 95^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in $CHCl_3$); IR (KBr): ν 3449 (N–H), 3067.6 (Ar–H stretching), 2973.3 (ali. C–H), 1728.3 (C=O), 1492 (C=N), 1272.2 (C–O), 710 (C–S), 1026, 858 cm^{-1} (characteristic of lactose); 1H NMR (δ in ppm, $CDCl_3$): 8.08–7.19 (50H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 2C₆H₅, C₆H₄), 4.78–3.56 (12H, m, lactosyl protons), 5.98–5.87 (2H, s, anomeric lactosyl protons); MS (*m/z*): 1511 (M^+), 1512 ($M^+ + 1$), 1474.5 ($M^+ - HCl$), 1053 (HBL⁺), 948 (HBL⁺-COC₆H₅), 932 (HBL⁺-COOC₆H₅), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found: C, 65.02; H, 4.12; N, 3.43; S, 4.12. Calcd. for $C_{82}H_{63}O_{17}N_4S_2Cl.HCl$: C, 65.12; H, 4.16; N, 3.70; S, 4.23%).

(3e): m.p. 114–116 °C; yield 68%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 65^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in $CHCl_3$) (Found: C, 66.52; H, 4.18; N, 3.22; S, 4.03. Calcd. for $C_{83}H_{66}O_{17}N_4S_2.HCl$: C, 66.82; H, 4.42; N, 3.75; S, 4.29%).

(3f): m.p. 106–108 °C; yield 74%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 72^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in $CHCl_3$) (Found: C, 66.42; H, 4.19; N, 3.12; S, 4.18. Calcd. for $C_{83}H_{66}O_{17}N_4S_2.HCl$: C, 66.82; H, 4.42; N, 3.75; S, 4.29%).

(3g): m.p. 138 °C; yield 78%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 118^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in $CHCl_3$): IR (KBr): ν 3466.5 (N–H), 3066.2 (Ar–H stretching), 2972.2 (ali. C–H), 1728.8 (C=O), 1492.7 (C=N), 1271.8 (C–O), 710.1 (C–S), 1026.2 cm^{-1} (characteristic of lactose); 1H NMR (δ in ppm, $CDCl_3$): 8.08–7.19 (49H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 2C₆H₅, C₆H₄), 4.99–3.71 (12H, m, lactosyl protons), 5.78–5.46 (2H, s,

anomeric lactosyl protons), 2.26 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); MS (*m/z*): 1490.5 (M^+), 1491.5 ($M^+ + 1$), 1454 ($M^+ - HCl$), 1385.5 ($M^+ - COC_6H_5$), 1369.5 ($M^+ - COOC_6H_5$), 1355.5 ($M^+ - CH_2COOC_6H_5$), 1053 (HBL⁺), 948 (HBL⁺-COC₆H₅), 932 (HBL⁺-COOC₆H₅), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found: C, 66.48; H, 4.28; N, 3.22; S, 4.03. Calcd. for $C_{83}H_{66}O_{17}N_4S_2.HCl$: C, 66.82; H, 4.42; N, 3.75; S, 4.29%).

HBL⁺ = Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl, TBG⁺ = Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glactosyl.

Antimicrobial activities:

All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup plate agar diffusion method by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. The compounds were taken at a concentration of 1 mg/ml using dimethyl sulphoxide as solvent. Amikacin (100 μ g/ml) was used as a standard for antibacterial activity and fluconazole (100 μ g/ml) as a standard for antifungal activity. The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Salmonella typhi* in nutrient agar medium and for antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and *Microsporum* in potato dextrose agar medium.

It has been observed that all of these synthesized compounds showed nearly the same inhibitory activity as that of the standard Amikacin and Fluconazole. Similarly it has also been observed that some of these compounds exhibited interesting microbial activities. 3a, 3b, 3d, 3f exhibited most significant activity against *Salmonella* and

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of compounds (5a-g)

Compd.	Antibacterial				Antifungal	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
3a	18	14	20	18	7	9
3b	23	13	13	22	10	7
3c	12	20	–	10	8	11
3d	22	17	22	24	7	–
3e	13	23	23	–	7	9
3f	18	15	17	20	7	8
3g	12	19	17	11	9	8
Amikacin	28	23	25	28	–	–
Fluconazole	–	–	–	–	18	21

E. coli while **3e** inhibited *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. All other compounds exhibited low to moderate activity.

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